

ACHIEVEMENTS OF UZBEK FOOTBALL IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE: ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7783763>

Abstract: After Uzbekistan gained independence, attention was paid to Uzbek football at the state level. In each region of our republic, consistent measures were taken to develop football infrastructure, raise the level of teams, and support young talents. As a result of this, together with our clubs, our national teams have been taking part in continental and international competitions. In this article, in the years of independence, the creation of regulatory and legal bases for the promotion of football, which has a large number of fans among popular sports in our country, as well as the achievements and results of Uzbek football in this period are analyzed in detail.

Keywords: Asian Games, national team, Asian Cup, Asian Champions League, career, Premier League, Fair play, football, futsal, Globe Soccer Awards.

INTRODUCTION

Football has a special place among modern sports. With its charm, popularity, wealth of uncompromising fights, it has become a favorite sport of millions of young and old in recent years. There is no person who is indifferent to football or has not kicked a ball at least once in his life...

In the years of independence, this type of sport, along with many other fields, began to be given importance at the state level. Under the initiative and leadership of the President, a wide range of measures have been implemented in order to develop the football infrastructure, to attract young people to this sport, especially to popularize children's football, to bring the country's football to the level of world standards. Dozens of football and academies have been established in each school of our republic, on a border-by-border basis, and have been created comfortably for our growing youth. Today, our boys and girls are learning the secrets of modern football in these places.

SUBJECT VALUABILITY AND CURRENT STATUS

The role of physical education in human health in the scientific research centers and universities of countries such as the USA, Great Britain, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, Brazil and Japan, the wide use of sports in establishing a healthy lifestyle among the population, organization of sports competitions and standardization of competition conditions, organization of international sports competitions and expansion of the ranks of countries participating in them, training of personnel in the field of physical education and sports, modernization and popularization of sports are being carried out. It should be noted that in the years of our country's independence, a number of decrees and decisions were adopted in order to further develop the football type of sport and strengthen the legal foundations of the field. For example, on January 17, 1996, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to fundamentally improve the organizational foundations and principles of football development in Uzbekistan" and "On measures to develop football in the Republic of

Uzbekistan" ", Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 1, 2006 "On additional measures to develop football in Uzbekistan", Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 3, 2017 "Physical Decision No. PQ-3031 on measures for the further development of education and mass sports, on December 4, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Measures to take the development of football in Uzbekistan to a completely new level" Decree No. PF-5887, Decree No. PF-5924 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 24, 2020 "On measures to further improve and popularize physical education and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan", on October 30, 2020 The adoption of Decree No. PF-6099 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the wide implementation of a healthy lifestyle and further development of mass sports" has created great opportunities for football and industry experts of our country [5]. According to the implementation of these decrees and decisions, promising changes are being made in the football of our country. Particular attention is paid to the work of training players, improving training systems and ensuring their effectiveness.

In Uzbekistan, effective mechanisms are being introduced to popularize football, promote a healthy lifestyle among the population, especially among young people, to adequately promote our country in international sports arenas, as well as to build, renovate and equip modern football fields. Therefore, researching the many years of experience in the development of football in our country during the years of independence from the perspective of a new theoretical methodology of the science of history is one of the urgent issues.

EXPERIMENTAL PART (RESEARCH IMPLEMENTATION)

Since 1992, the national championship of Uzbekistan has been started. This historical event was a sign that a new page was opened in the football of our country. That year, 17 teams participated in the Premier League, 18 in the First League, and 42 in the Second League. Every game of the High League was intense. In particular, the fights for the title of the championship of Uzbekistan took place mainly between the capital team, as well as between the clubs "Neftchi" (Fergana), "Nurafshan" (Bukhara) and "Sogdiyona" (Jizzakh). In general, the teams "Pakhtakor", "Bunyodkor", "Neftchi", "Navbahor", MHSK (Central Military Sports Club), "Dostlik", "Lokomotiv" won the championship in our national championship [2, 64 b.]. Among them, the prizes of "Pakhtakor" representatives are somewhat significant, for example, the capital team won more victories than other teams in the national championship and cup competitions. On May 21, 1994, the Football Federation of Uzbekistan (now the Football Association of Uzbekistan - UFA) was established. Soon, in June, it became a member of the Association of International Football Federations, and in December of the Asian Football Confederation. In the same year, our players were officially introduced at the major sports forum in the Asian region - the XII Asian Games held in Japan.

Moreover, our national clubs have been defending the honor of our country in the Asian Champions League competition for several years now. In short, Uzbek football has traveled a difficult path in a short period of history. Most importantly, this sport has become one of the most popular and popular games in our country. During the past period, great achievements and remarkable results were recorded in sports, including football, as well as in other fields. We will talk about these below. After Uzbekistan gained independence, the victories did not wait long. The 1994 Asian Summer Games held in the Japanese cities of Hiroshima, Onomiti and Miyoshi are still remembered with vivid memories. The reason is that the national team of Uzbekistan, which participated in this competition, won the championship. Our compatriots

defeated Saudi Arabia, Malaysia, Hong Kong and Thailand in Group "V" and reached the quarter-finals with a 100% result. At this stage, Turkmenistan was also surrendered in a big way. Our representatives defeated South Korea in the 1/2 finals. In the decisive competition, China was also left behind, and our team won the main prize for our country. This competition was the first major international competition for our representatives. Despite this, our players reached the finals of the competition, eventually defeated the Chinese national team and returned to our country with gold medals [6, 7 p.]. Mirjalal Kasimov, Azamat Abduraimov, Ilhom Sharipov, Sergey Lebedov, Igor Shkvirin, Andrei Fyodorov, Shuhrat Maksudov, Abdukakhor Ma'rufaliev, Alexander Tikhonov, Farhod Magomedov and a number of other talented players were in the ranks of this national team [8, 10 b].

Mahmud Rahimov was one of the people who made a great contribution to the rise of Uzbek football during the years of independence. He was born on June 1, 1955. This future coach, who played mainly in second league teams in his football career, started the first part of his career in our national football as an organizer. In 1996, Mahmud Rahimov was appointed the head of Dostlik club. The beginning of his bright moments in coaching dates back to 1995. In the same year, the specialist was invited to the "Dostlik" team of the Tashkent region as a head coach, and in a short time he made his students among the strongest. Thanks to these successes, Rahimov became the head of the national team of Uzbekistan in 1998. A year later, he started coaching our national team. Our representatives achieved excellent results in the qualifying round of the Asian Championship, the first competition under Mahmud Rahimov. The national team won six out of seven matches. They lost to Thailand (0:1) in the only match that did not decide anything. The national team of Uzbekistan rose to the 55th place in the FIFA ranking for the first time in its history [4, 12 p.]. In 1999, he was named the "Best Coach of the Year" by the Asian Football Confederation. Unfortunately, a car accident took him away from this bright world early.

Also, Rauf Inileev, who started his career as a football player and continued as a football coach, has his place in Uzbek football. He was born on October 8, 1950 in Tashkent. In his football career, he defended the honor of "Pakhtakor" and "Start" teams of Tashkent, "Mehnat" and "Zvezda" teams of Jizzakh. Rauf Inileev started his coaching career in the "Zvezda" club. In 2006, he led the youth national team of Uzbekistan. A year later, he became the coach of our national team. In the same year, he participated in the Asian Games in Qatar [20].

In 2007, our team took part in the Asian Cup and went to the playoffs with the second place in the group with Iran. In the quarter-finals, we lost to Saudi Arabia by one goal. But our compatriots played beautiful and meaningful games. In the same year, Rauf Inileev was awarded "The best coach of the year" by Uzbekistan and AFC [19]. Server Jeparov, an experienced football player who made a worthy contribution to the rise of Uzbek football, was born on October 3, 1982 in the city of Chirchik, Tashkent region. At the age of 36, our midfielder, who still kicks the ball, started his career in "Navbahor" and is currently defending the honor of "Metallurg". Server, who moved to "Bunyodkor" in 2008, showed bright games, reached the semi-finals of the AFC Champions League with his team, and was named the "Best Player of the Year" by the AFC. In 2011, our country was recognized on a continental scale. With this, Server Djeparov became the first Uzbek to be named "Best Footballer of the Year"

twice in Asia. In addition, he was recognized as the best player in Uzbekistan in 2008 and 2010 [19].

In 2015, Dostonbek Hamdamov, who defended the honor of "Bunyodkor" club of Tashkent, was recognized as "the best young player of Asia". At the awarding ceremony of the best of the Asian continent in 2015 in Delhi, India, it was clear that the "Best young player of the year" award will be given to the "Bunyodkor" player. Because in the list of the final three of this nomination, three representatives of the "Swallows" were Dostonbek Hamdamov, Zabihillo Orinboev and Eldor Shomurodov. All three players spent the last season very well. Each of them deserved and deserved to be the best. AFC awarded the prize to Dostonbek Hamdamov [8, 12 p.]. Hamdamov played great games for the youth national team of Uzbekistan at the World Championship held in New Zealand.

At this point, it is appropriate to acknowledge the work of Eldor Shomurodov, who has graduated from the Uzbek football school, plays for the prestigious football teams of the world, and has become the pride of football fans in our country. Eldor, one of the famous and talented young people who grew up in the Surkhan oasis, was born on June 29, 1995 in the city of Zharkurgan. He started playing football at the age of 6. At the age of 11, he began studying at the Mash'al football club academy in Mubarak. Starting from 2014, at the age of 19, he began to be involved in the main team of the club and played in 10 matches that season, and "Mash'al" took the fifth place in the championship of Uzbekistan. Since then, Eldor has been involved in the youth national team of Uzbekistan [12]. At the beginning of 2015, Eldor joined the ranks of the players of the Tashkent club "Bunyodkor" and played there until June 2017. As part of this club, he played in 96 games and scored 20 goals (Uzbek Oliy League, Uzbek Cup and Asian Champions League). Together with "Bunyodkor" he became a finalist of the Cup of Uzbekistan and won silver medals of the Championship of Uzbekistan [12].

At the end of 2015, although he was among the candidates for the "Best Young Footballer of Asia" nomination at the AFC, in the end, our compatriot Dostonbek Hamdamov, who is the same age as Shomurodov, won. In July 2017, Eldor moved to the Russian club "Rostov" and signed a 2.5-year contract with the club. At the end of May 2019, "Rostov" extended the contract with Shomurodov for three years, and on June 7, for five years. In August 2019, he was named the best player of the month in the Premier League. In the 2019-2020 season, he scored 11 goals in 28 matches of the Russian championship [13].

Eldor Shomurodov transferred to the Italian club "Genoa" on October 1, 2020. The transfer amount was 7.5 million euros. The player signed a contract with the club "Genoa" until the summer of 2024 [14]. Shomurodov became the second Uzbek player in history after Ilyas Zeytullaev in the Italian championship. On October 19 of the same year, he made his Serie A debut in a match against "Verona" (0:0) [15]. On November 30, he scored his first goal for Genoa in the second half of Serie A at home against Parma [16]. On August 2, 2021, Eldor transferred to "Roma", the contract amount was 17.5 million euros. On 19 August 2021, Eldor made his debut for his new club in the Conference League qualifying play-off against Trabzonspor, where he scored his first goal in a match that ended in victory for the Romans [17].

In 1998, the national team of Uzbekistan took part in the next summer Asian Games. Our compatriots competed with Kuwait and Mongolia in Group "G". In the first round, our representatives drew 3:3 against the Kuwaitis. In the next game, they scored 15 unanswered goals against Mongolia [18]. It is noteworthy that this result is the biggest victory in the

history of our football. In the quarter-finals, our national team lost to Iran and bid farewell to the competition.

In recent years, the achievements in our football were achieved when Mirabror Usmanov was the head of our football. One of them is the "Fair play" award of FIFA. The value of this prize is very high. Because this is the fate of few countries in the world. On January 7, 2013, in Zurich, Switzerland, Mirabror Usmanov received the award, which is presented to the federation that promotes and adheres to halal football [19]. Mirabror Usmanov, who was the head of football of Uzbekistan from 2005 to 2017, paid great attention to the infrastructure of the clubs. Including stadiums. Dilapidated arenas were renovated, stadiums were built for teams that did not have a playground. All football fields have been modernized. A playground was built for the "Bunyodkor" club based on the latest standards [7, p. 105]. In those years, the "Bunyodkor" arena was recognized as the best in Central Asia. There are also enviable stadiums in the regions. For example, "Central" playgrounds in Karshi and Namangan are among them.

Mirabror Usmanov, who did great things for the development of our football, left with one dream, as he said. Even he could not see the participation of the national team of Uzbekistan in the world championship. Usmanov died on March 15, 2019, after leaving OFF.

The flag team of our country "Pakhtakor" became the winner not only in the domestic championship, but also in the international arena. In 2007, in the Commonwealth Champions Cup, the Tashkent team competed with Latvian, Armenian and Ukrainian clubs in group "S" and went to the playoffs with the first place. In the quarter finals, our compatriots defeated the Serbian "OFK Belgrade" team. Moldavian club "Sherif" was defeated in the semi-finals. After a draw with the Latvians was recorded in the decisive match, luck smiled on the representatives of "Pakhtakor" in the penalty shootout [18]. Thus, the capital city won the cup. It is noteworthy that Pakhtakor reached the finals the following year as well [19]. In 1994, Fergana's "Neftchi" club also played in the final.

Undoubtedly, the most prestigious league of our continent is the OCL. Many of our clubs defended the honor of our country in this competition. However, no one has been lucky enough to become the champion so far. Two teams from Tashkent - "Pakhtakor" and "Bunyodkor" - reached the semi-finals twice. In 2002-2003, "Lions" took place in the same group with much stronger teams. In order to advance to the next stage, our representatives competed with Iran's "Persepolis", Iraq's "Al Talaba" and Turkmenistan's "Nisa" and won the first place. In the playoffs, our compatriots lost to Thailand's "Tero Sasana" by two games and were eliminated from the finals [19]. In 2004, Pakhtakor chilar tried to get out of the group with Iran's Zob Ahan, Qatar's Qatar SK and Bahrain's Riffa. "Pakhtakor", which went to the quarter-finals with the first place, overtook "Al Wahda" of the UAE. In the semi-finals, South Korea's "Songnam Ilhwa Chhunma" club stopped its progress in the competition [6].

"Bunyodkor" was established in 2005 under the name "Quruchchi" and gained fame in a short time. He took the lead in the domestic championship. It caused a commotion on the international stage as well. Especially, the debut in the OCL reached the semi-finals. In 2008, the "Swallows" took the first place in the group, competing with Saudi Arabia's "Al Ittihad", Iran's "Sepakhan" and Syria's "Al Ittihad". Another Iranian club "Saipa" was defeated in the quarter finals. In the semi-final, the team of Tashkent, who faced the Australian team "Adelaide United", failed to reach the final due to the results of two matches [19].

"Swallows" survived the "group of death" in 2012. Australia's Adelaide United, South Korea's Pohang Steelers and Japan's Gamba Osaka took second place. Sonnam Ilhwa Chhonma of South Korea was defeated in the playoff. "Builders" who tried their best against "Adelaide United" in the quarter-finals, won the previous semi-final. At the next stage, South Korea's "Ulsan Hyeonde" team lost their chance [19].

The AFC Cup, which is considered the number two competition in Asia, was brought to our country once. This happened in 2011. Having defeated Indian "Dempo", Lebanese "Al Ansar" and Yemeni "Al Tilyal", "Nasaf" took the first place in the group with a hundred percent result. The Jordanian team "Al Faisali" was defeated in the playoffs. In the quarter-finals, Thailand's "Chonburi" and Jordan's "Al Vikhdat" clubs were left behind in the next round. The opponents, who held the final at home, defeated the Kuwaiti team "El Kuwait" by one goal and became the winner of the main prize [18]. This success opened a new page in the history of "Nasaf".

Life is very interesting. In 2008, when Uzbekistan hosted the Asian Championship among 16-year-olds, Iran won the championship. Four years later, our team won the competition held in Iran. Our national team led by Dilshod Nuraliev took the second place in the group after competing with equals from Syria, China and India. South Korea was defeated in the quarter-finals and Iran in the semi-finals. In the decisive match, Japan was defeated and won the championship [18].

It is noteworthy that in 2010, the continental championship among U-16 was held in our country and our national team participated in the final. But due to the mistakes of the judges, we were satisfied with the second place.

Chinese fields are also considered lucky for us. We remember this country with bright memories. Because in 2018, at the Asian Championship among under-23s, our national team played great games and took the top place of the podium thanks to beautiful victories. In this competition, Ravshan Haydarov's students lost to Qatar in the 1st round. But they won the next matches and finished the group stage with the second place. Our representatives, hungry for the quarter finals, scored 4 unanswered goals against Japan. We beat South Korea 4:1 in the semi-finals. In the final, we played against Vietnam and won the main prize thanks to a goal scored in the last minute of overtime [19]. It is clear that this game has been preserved in the memory of the fans under the name "snowy final". A few years later, Ravshan Haydarov, who won the Commonwealth Champions Cup with the Pakhtakor club, won the Asian Championship with the Olympic team of Uzbekistan.

At the 2011 U-17 World Championship held in Mexico and the 2013 U-20 World Championship held in Turkey, members of the Uzbekistan national team reached the quarter-finals. won the award. The youth lost to their peers from Uruguay (0:2), and they lost 4:0 to the French players, whose youth team included future stars such as Pogba, Umtiti, Dine.[18]

Uzbek football is spreading more and more to the world under the name of Ravshan Ermatov. Ermatov, unlike our national team, regularly participates in the World Championship. Our compatriot managed 11 matches in the World Cup and became an absolute record holder. At the 2010 World Cup, which was initially held in South Africa, Ravshan Ermatov refereed 5 matches: 3 in the group stage, one in the quarter-finals and one in the semi-finals. In 2014, he worked in 4 matches in Brazil: 3 in the group and one in the quarter-finals. At the last World Cup, Ravshan Ermatov refereed 2 matches in the group stage [21]. Due to the recurrence of the old injury of the wing referee, Ermatov's brigade did not work in other matches.

Also, Ravshan Ermatov worked in other prestigious tournaments in addition to continental level games. In particular, in 2008, he managed the quarter and final match between the clubs. In 2011, he played in the 5th place match and the final at the World Club Championship. In 2017, he refereed the second round match of this competition. In 2013, he managed one match at the Confederations Cup. It is noteworthy that Ravshan Ermatov, who is a FIFA referee, won the world-wide "Globe Soccer Awards" prize in 2015 [21].

The national team of amputees of Uzbekistan, consisting of players with disabilities, has its own reputation in world football. Our amputees are the winners of the 1990, 1991, 2007, 2010, 2012 world championships. In the final of the 2007 competition, the Uzbek players defeated Russia, and in the tournament held in Argentina in 2010, our compatriots defeated the hosts with a score of 3:1. At the 2012 World Championship, our national team won 1:0 against the Russians[22].

Futsal has its fans in our country, like football. Due to the good attention paid to this sport in our country, since 1999, the championship of the continent has been entrusted to Uzbekistan 3 times. Our futsal players reached the final in all of them. In general, we took 3rd place in futsal 3 times. Our representatives participated in 4 finals and lost to Iran in 3 of them [23]. If there were no Persians, would we have won the Asian championship at least 3 times?!

When the national team played, there were times when the fans could not fit in the arenas. Especially at the last Asian Championship held in Tashkent, our compatriots showed a very convincing game and reached the final, and the audience supported our national team wonderfully. Our compatriots were lucky in the decisive competition. However, he qualified for the World Championship held in the fall of 2016. In the matches hosted by Colombia, our futsal players lost to Portugal and Panama in the group. But the draw with the home team is important. Our team earned one point in its debut at the World Championship [23].

To date, the national football team of Uzbekistan has played a total of 312 official and friendly matches, of which 150 were won, 58 were drawn, and 104 were lost. encountered [20].

RESULTS ANALYSIS AND CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that after gaining independence, attention was paid to Uzbek football at the state level. It is worth mentioning that thanks to independence, a new spirit has entered our football. An important and gradual stage of reforms has begun. In each region of our republic, consistent measures were taken to develop football infrastructure, raise the level of teams, and support young talents.

Dozens of facilities, football schools and academies are being built in every region of our republic, modern conditions and comfortable opportunities are being created for our growing youth. As a result of this, together with our clubs, our national teams have been taking part in continental and international competitions. When it comes to this, the successful participation of our junior and youth national team in the Asian and World Championships should be specially recognized. One of the biggest tasks facing Uzbek football is to ensure the participation of our national team in the final stage of the World Cup. To date, the national football team of Uzbekistan has participated in the qualifiers for the World Championships eight times and failed. Of course, in the history of the national team, there were times when only one goal or one victory was not enough to reach the World Cup, even when its victory was canceled

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